

General Cunningham

Brit Museum.

July 6. 1891.

My dear Sir

On my return from fern? I found the parcel of photos: wh: you so kindly sent me, wh: I need hardly say will be of very great use to me. While in Germany I saw at the Berlin Mus: specimens of some of the sculpt: from Buddha Gaya somewhat erroneously. I believe Dr Bastian got them when he went to India.

With regard to the Amaravati sculptures, they are nearly all set up, and the glazing will I hope be completed in a week or two. To show you that we do not grudge money ^{for such objects} I may mention that the glazing will cost nearly £500 but I hope that at any rate the decay of these precious relics will be stopped.

As to the Bharhut sculpt: I consider them the most interesting Buddhist remain that have ever been discover'd. I cannot imagine what Thomas can be about, finding sun worship an libitum, turning fruits into horse's heads and throwing doubts on the antiquity of the inscriptions on the bas-reliefs - I hope to give him a turn on the subject presently in a paper I have been writing on the Amaravati of which I trust to send you a copy as soon as it is printed. As to casts ^{of the sculptures wh: you kindly offer to get for us} I think I sh^d like to wait a little, as the birds & casts are not yet gone. With renewed thanks
Believe me yours truly